

Oxidative Debenzylation and Cyclisation of 1,5-Disubstituted 2-S-Benzyliso-4-thiobiurets: Formation of 3,5-Disubstituted Imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines or/and the Related *N*-2-Benzothiazolyl-*N'*-substituted-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides and 1,2,4-Thiadiazolines

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Bromine and iodine in hot concentrated solutions in chloroform or benzene have been found to effect debenzylation of the 1,5-diaryl- and 1-alkyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets, followed by ring closure to the related 3,5-disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines. Depending on the reaction conditions, smaller or larger quantities of the related *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-substituted-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides are produced simultaneously. When the substituents in positions 1,5 in the starting isodithiobiuret are an aryl and alkyl group respectively, the related 3,5-disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine is the sole product. Similarly, when both 1,5-positions are substituted by alkyl groups, the related dithiazolidines or the 1,2,4-thiadiazolines are the main products.

The earlier work on the chemistry of dithiobiurets and their derivatives¹ has now been extended to an investigation of the interaction of bromine (and in certain cases of iodine) and 1,5-diaryl-, 1-alkyl-5-aryl-, 1-aryl-5-alkyl-, and 1,5-dialkyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets.

In concentrated benzene or chloroform solutions, the reaction of bromine or iodine with 1,5-diaryl- and 1-alkyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets (I) appears to proceed in two directions, leading to (i) the debenzylation of the isodithiobiuret followed by ring closure to the related 3,5-disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (II) and (ii) *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-substituted-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (III):

(where R and R' are both aryl groups or R is alkyl and R', aryl group)

1. Dixit, *This Journal*, 1960, **37**, 151; 1961, **38**, 44, 221; 1962, **39**, 263; Joshua, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 155; Joshi and Verma, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 989.

The relative proportion of the hydrobromides of (II) and (III) in the oxidation product depends on the conditions of reaction: higher concentration of the reactants and higher reaction temperature are conducive to larger yields of (II), whereas under more mild conditions compound (III) predominates. In ethanolic media compound (III) is the exclusive product.

The 1,5-dialkyl- and 1-aryl-5-alkyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets on oxidation under analogous conditions afford mainly the dithiazolidines (II) where the substituents in positions 3 and 5 are both alkyl residues or an alkyl and aryl group respectively. In the case of 1,5-dimethyl- and 1-methyl-5-ethyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets, in addition to the related dithiazolidines (IV), the thiadiazolines (V) were also obtained:

(where R=Me or Et group)

The identity of the dithiazolidines (II) has been established by comparison with authentic samples of these, preparation of which has been already described². The related 2,4-dithiobiurets have also been obtained in some cases by their reduction and have been found identical with authentic samples prepared by the sulphide reduction of the corresponding 2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets.

The benzothiazolyliothiocarbamides (VII) have been synthesised by an alternative route:

The identity of the products (III) has been established with (VII) by undepressed melting points of their mixtures. In some cases the *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (III) have been debenzylated by reduction with alkaline sulphide and the thiocarbamides, so formed, found identical with those prepared by the above route (VI)³.

2. Dixit, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 407.

3. Joshua, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 621.

EXPERIMENTAL

*Oxidation of 1,5-Diaryl-, 1,5-Dialkyl-, 1-Aryl-5-alkyl-, and 1-Alkyl-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets by Bromine: Formation of 3,5-Disubstituted Imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines or/and the related N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-substituted-S-benzylisothiocarbamides**

The isodithiobiuret was suspended in chloroform or benzene and bromine in chloroform or benzene was added gradually when the isodithiobiuret went into solution; a product separated on standing or on addition of ethanol. This was a mixture of the hydrobromides of the related 3,5-disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines and *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-substituted-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides. The mixture of the hydrobromides on treatment with ammonia afforded a mixture of the respective free bases which were separated by ether in which *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-substituted-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides dissolved, leaving behind the insoluble 3,5-disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines. In all cases, the products were crystallised from ethanol. The proportion of the salts of the above two bases in the oxidation product was found to depend on the conditions of the reaction. The more concentrated solutions of the reactants favoured formation of dithiazolidines in greater yield, whereas with increasing dilution the *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-substituted-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides were the main products. For example: When to 1,5-diphenyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret (5 g.), suspended in chloroform (5 ml), bromine (1.2 ml) in chloroform (2 ml) was added with stirring, gradually the isodithiobiuret went into solution with evolution of much heat. On keeping, a sticky mass separated which dissolved on addition of ethanol (20 ml) and subsequently a crystalline product separated. The product was treated with ammonia and the free base (3.3 g.) was filtered, dried, and extracted with ether. The residue (2.1 g.) was identified with 3,5-diphenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine; crystals from ethanol, m.p. 177-78°. The soluble portion (1.2 g.) on crystallisation was found to be *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-phenyl-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide, m.p. 133°. Thus the yields of dithiazolidine and isothiocarbamide were 56% and 24% respectively. In another experiment, 1,5-diphenyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret (5 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (20 ml) and bromine (1.2 ml) in chloroform (10 ml) was added with stirring. The hydrobromides separated as a sticky mass which went into solution on addition of ethanol and then reprecipitated as a crystalline powder. The solid product was filtered, dried, and treated with ammonia, followed by extraction with ether. The ether-insoluble residue (0.50 g.) was found to be 3,5-diphenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine, m.p. 177-78°. The soluble part (3.2 g.) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 133°, and was identified with *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-phenyl-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide. The yields of dithiazolidine and isothiocarbamide were 15% and 64% respectively. The results of these experiments have been summarised in Table I.

Oxidation of 1,5-Diphenyl- and 1,5-Di-p-tolyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets by Iodine

(i). *In Hot Concentrated Solution in Chloroform.*—(a). To a boiling solution of 1,5-diphenyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret (5 g.) in chloroform (10 ml) was gradually added an excess of a hot solution of iodine (about 4 g.) in chloroform (30 ml). Iodine was instantaneously consumed. The solvent was evaporated and the product treated with ethanol

*Only in case of 1,5-dimethyl- and 1-methyl-5-ethyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets, 1,2,4-thiadiazolines were obtained (vide Table I).

when it granulated; it was filtered and dried. 3, 5-Diphenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydriodide, so formed, was crystallised from ethanol; m.p. 188°. (Found: Equiv., 410. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{12}N_3S_2I$: Equiv., 413). The hydriodide on treatment with ammonia gave the free base, m.p. 177-78°. It did not show any depression in m.p. when mixed with the product described above. The hydriodide yield was 62%.

TABLE I

Oxidation of 1,5-disubstituted-2-S-benzyliso-4-thioburets by bromine in chloroform or benzene.

S.No.	1,5-Disubstituted 2-S-benzyliso-4-thioburet oxidised.	Oxidation products formed: (a) 3,5-Disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine. (b) N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-substituted-S-benzylisothiocarbamide.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1	1,5-Diphenyl-	(a) 3,5-Diphenylimino- ($C_{14}H_{11}N_3S_2$)	177-78°	C : 59.76% H : 4.14 N : 14.89	58.90% 3.95 14.72
		(b) N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-phenyl- ($C_{21}H_{17}N_3S_2$)	133°	C : 66.47 H : 4.26 N : 11.28	67.20 4.52 11.20
2	1,5-Di-p-tolyl-	(a) 3,5-Di-p-tolylimino- ($C_{16}H_{13}N_3S_2$)	166°	C : 61.02 H : 5.41 N : 13.18	61.34 4.78 13.41
		(b) N-2-(6)-Methylbenzothiazolyl-N'-p-tolyl- ($C_{23}H_{21}N_3S_2$)	155-56°	C : 68.00 H : 5.44 N : 10.28	68.48 5.21 10.42
3	1,5-Di-o-tolyl-	(a) 3,5-Di-o-tolylimino- ($C_{16}H_{13}N_3S_2$)	166°	C : 60.80 H : 4.68 N : 13.18	61.34 4.78 13.41
		(b) N-2-(4)-Methylbenzothiazolyl-N'-o-tolyl- ($C_{23}H_{21}N_3S_2$)	91°	C : 68.39 H : 5.41 N : 10.20	68.48 5.21 10.42
4	1,5-Di-p-phenetyl-	(a) 3,5-Di-p-phenetylimino- ($C_{18}H_{15}O_2N_3S_2$)	186°	C : 58.23 H : 4.84 N : 11.22	57.90 5.09 11.28
		(b) N-2-(6)-Ethoxybenzothiazolyl-N-p-phenetyl- ($C_{25}H_{23}O_2N_3S_2$)	114°	C : 65.02 H : 4.91 N : 9.25	64.79 5.39 9.07
5	1-p-Tolyl-5-phenyl-	(a) 5-p-Tolylimino-3-phenylimino- ($C_{15}H_{13}N_3S_2$)	198°	C : 57.57 H : 4.41 N : 14.53	60.20 4.34 14.79
		(b) N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-p-tolyl- ($C_{22}H_{19}N_3S_2$)	128°	C : 67.52 H : 5.38 N : 10.56	67.96 4.88 10.76

TABLE I (contd.)

S.No.	1,5-Dimethyl-2- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-4-thiobiuret oxidised.	Oxidation products formed: (a) 3,5-Dimethylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine. (b) <i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -substituted- <i>S</i> -benzylisothiocarbamide.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd..
6.	1-Phenyl-5-methyl-	(a) 5-Phenylimino-3-methylimino-Hydrobromide m.p. 198°. Equiv. found 302; calc. 304 (C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂)	134°	C : 49.18% H : 4.21 N : 18.79	49.43% 4.03 18.83
7.	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-methyl-	(a) 5- <i>p</i> -Tolylimino-3-methylimino-Hydrobromide m.p. 231°. Equiv. found 316; calc. 318 (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂)	161°	C : 50.45 H : 4.32 N : 17.38	50.63 4.64 17.72
8.	1-Methyl-5-phenyl-	(a) 5-Methylimino-3-phenylimino-	Found identical with the product described under (6).		
		(b) <i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -methyl-(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	119°	N : 12.98 S : 20.79	13.41 20.47
9.	1-Methyl-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	(a) 5-Methylimino-3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-	Found identical with the product described under (7).		
		(b) <i>N</i> -2-(6)-Methylbenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -methyl-(C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	114°	N : 12.72	12.64
10.	1,5-Dimethyl-	(a) 3,5-Dimethylimino-Hydrobromide m. p. 278°. Equiv. found 238; calc. 242 (C ₈ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂)	167°	C : 31.52 H : 4.94 N : 25.68 S : 39.89	29.81 4.36 26.08 39.75
		and			
		2,5-Dimethyl-3- <i>S</i> -benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazoline (C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	67°	C : 52.46 H : 5.09 N : 16.82	52.58 5.17 16.73
11.	1-methyl-5-ethyl-	(a) 5-Methylimino-3-ethylimino-Hydrobromide m. p. 228°. Equiv. found 258; calc. 256 (C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂)	158°	C : 36.04 H : 5.47 N : 23.98	34.28 5.14 24.00
		and			
		2-Methyl-5-ethyl-3- <i>S</i> -benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazoline as picrate (C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₇ N ₃ S ₂)	138-39°	N : 17.32	17.00

These were found identical with the respective authentic dithiazolidines.

(b). Similarly oxidised with iodine, the 1,5-di-*p*-tolyl 2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret afforded 5-*p*-tolylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydriodide, m.p. 212° (yield 66%, equiv. found, 438; calc. for C₁₈H₁₈N₃IS₂: 441). Free base, m.p. 198°. This did not show depression in m.p. when mixed with the product obtained by bromine oxidation (*vide supra*).

(ii) *In Dilute Solution in Cold Chloroform*.—To 1,5-diphenyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret (5 g.), dissolved in chloroform (25 ml), a solution of iodine (4 g.) in chloroform (50 ml) was added gradually. On evaporation of the solvent and treatment with ethanol, the product solidified to a crystalline powder, m.p. 148°. It was identified with *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-phenyl-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide hydriodide (Equiv. found: 49%; calc. for $C_{21}H_{19}N_3IS_2$: 503). The free base m.p. 133°. This did not show depression in m.p. when mixed with *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-phenyl-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide, described above.

Preparation of N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-2-substituted-S-benzylisothiocarbamides

The required *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-substituted thiocarbamides were prepared by condensation of the appropriate 2-amino- and 2-amino-substituted benzothiazoles and aryl- or alkylisothiocyanates (cf. Joshua³). These and benzyl chloride (1:1 molecular ratio), when heated together under reflux for about 15 minutes, afforded the hydrochlorides of the related *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides, which on treatment with ammonia furnished free bases. These were crystallised from ethanol. These did not show depression in m.p. when mixed with the products described in Table I. The following *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-substituted-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides were prepared (Table II).

TABLE II

S.No.	Reactants.	Product formed (as free base).	M.P.
1.	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -phenyl-T* and BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -phenyl-I†	133°
2.	<i>N</i> -2-(6)-Methylbenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> - <i>p</i> -tolyl-T and BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-(6)-Methylbenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> - <i>p</i> -tolyl-I	155-56°
3.	<i>N</i> -2-(4)-Methylbenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> - <i>o</i> -tolyl-T and BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-(4)-Methylbenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> - <i>o</i> -tolyl-I	89-90°
4.	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> - <i>p</i> -tolyl-T and BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> - <i>p</i> -tolyl-I	128°
5.	<i>N</i> -2-(6)-Ethoxybenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> - <i>p</i> -phenetyl-T and BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-(6)-Ethoxybenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> - <i>p</i> -phenetyl-I	114°
6.	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -methyl-T and BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -methyl-I	119°
7.	<i>N</i> -2-(6)-Methylbenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -methyl-T and BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-(6)-Methylbenzothiazolyl- <i>N'</i> -methyl-I	114°

*T denotes thiocarbamide.

†I denotes *S*-benzylisothiocarbamide.

*Reduction of 3,5-Disubstituted Imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines by Ammonium Sulphide:
Formation of Related 1,5-Disubstituted 2,4-Dithiobiurets*

To 3,5-diphenyl-, 3,5-di-*p*-tolyl-, 3,5-di-*p*-phenetyl-, 1-*p*-tolyl-5-phenyl-, 5-phenyl-3-methyl-, and 3,5-dimethyl-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines, dissolved in hot ethanolic ammonium sulphide, a stream of H_2S was passed for 15-30 minutes. The clear

solution on acidification or dilution with water precipitated the related 1,5-disubstituted 2,4-dithiobiurets. These were crystallised from ethanol: 1,5-diphenyl-, m.p. 144-45°; 1,5-di-*p*-tolyl-, m.p. 141-42°; 1,5-di-*p*-phenetyl-, m.p. 151°; 1-*p*-tolyl-5-phenyl-, m.p. 149°; 1-phenyl-5-methyl-, m.p. 132°; 1,5-dimethyl-, m.p. 148°. Identity of each of these was established by observing undepressed mixed melting points with authentic samples of the appropriate 1,5-disubstituted 2,4-dithiobiurets².

*Debenzylation of N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-substituted-S-benzylisothiocarbamides
by Alkaline Hydrogen Sulphide*

To *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-phenyl- and *N*-2(4)-methylbenzothiazolyl-*N'*-*o*-tolyl-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides, dissolved in ethanolic ammonia, H₂S was passed for 3 to 4 hours. Products separating were filtered, dried, and crystallised. These were found identical with *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide (m.p. 200°) and *N*-2(4)-methylbenzothiazolyl-*N'*-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide (m.p. 184°) respectively (cf Joshua³).

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